

High-Spin Manganese(II) Chelates

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A survey of the literature indicates that there is no record of manganese(II) complexes of 1-amidino-2-thiourea and substituted 1-amidino-2-thioureas. Rây et al prepared nickel(II), copper(II), cobalt (II & III) and palladium (II) complexes of 1-amidino-2-thiourea and observed that few metals were precipitated as their sulphides¹⁻³. This observation has been explored for quantitative estimation of certain metal ions⁴. Recently Paigankar and Haldar have reported the synthesis of nickel (II), copper(II) and cobalt (III) complexes of 1-amidino-8-ethylthiourea⁵. The present communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of two new four co-ordinated manganese(II) chelates, the ligands used being 1-amidino-2-thiourea and 1-amidino-8-ethylthiourea.

The complexes were prepared by refluxing an ethanolic solution of manganous chloride (1 mole) and the appropriate ligand (2 mole) for an hour. The separated crystalline compounds were filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried in air. 1-Amidino-2-thiourea and 1-amidino-8-ethylthiourea were prepared according to the published procedures⁶⁻⁷. The complexes are stable and do not decompose or oxidise even on heating at 120° for hours. These are insoluble in chloroform, ether, benzene, nitrobenzene, sparingly soluble in ethanol but soluble in methanol. In methanol solution, the complexes slowly undergo oxidation presumably to manganese(III) state with deepening of colour from yellow to chocolate red. However, the freshly prepared methanol solution is pale yellow in colour and behaves as a non-electrolyte ($\Lambda_M \sim 3$ mhos). Besides during the entire course of oxidation, there was no significant change in the conductance values. This points to the fact that oxidised product, too is a non-electrolyte.

Although six-coordinated complexes of bivalent manganese are very common⁸, the four co-ordinated manganese(II) complexes are rare. The magnetic moments of these complexes were determined at room temperature by the Gouy method. Diamagnetic correction of the ligands was applied by the use of Pascal's constants⁹. Diamagnetism of the electron system of the manganous ion was also taken into account. The magnetic

1. P. Rây *Chem. Revs.*, 1961, **61**, 313.
2. P. Rây and A. K. Chaudhury, *This Journal*, 1950, **27**, 673.
3. P. Rây, and S. N. Poddar, *This Journal*, 1952, **29**, 279.
4. R. A. Nadkarni and B. C. Haldar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 427; 1965, **3**, 539; *This Journal*, 1964, **41**, 319, 813; 1965, **42**, 5; 1967, **44**, 162.
5. A. Paigankar and B. C. Haldar, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 175.
6. F. Kurzer, *Organic Synthesis*, 1955, **35**, 69, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York.
7. F. Kurzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, p. 1.
8. N. Goldenberg, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 847.
9. P. W. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1955, p-92.

moments of these complexes are invariably 5.8 B. M. (Table I). This value clearly agrees with the high spin tetrahedral structure with manganese(II) in the 6s state¹⁰.

TABLE I

Analysis, Colour, Molar conductance and Magnetic susceptibility data of the Complexes

Compound	Colour	Analysis		Molar conductance mhos	Magnetic moment (B.M.) T=304°K
		Found %	Reqd. %		
Bis-1-amidino-2-thiourea-Mn (II) [Mn (ATU) ₂]	Brownish yellow	Mn, 19.2	19.0	3.0	5.85
		N, 38.5	38.7		
Bis-1-amidino-3-ethylthiourea Mn(II) [Mn (ASETU) ₂]	Dirty yellow	Mn, 16.1	15.9	3.2	5.83
		N, 32.2	32.4		

The insolubility of these complexes in common solvents did not permit any evaluation of molecular size and determination of electronic absorption spectra in solution.

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10. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc. New York, 1962, p. 701.